

Catalytic synthesis of polyhydroquinolines by lithium perchlorate in polyethylene glycol

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Abstract : An efficient synthesis of polyhydroquinolines is achieved via a four-component reaction of aldehydes, dimedone, ethyl acetoacetate, and ammonium acetate in one-pot in the presence of LiClO_4 in polyethylene glycol (PEG). This procedure tolerates most of substrates and has the advantages of short routine, high yields, and low environmental impact.

Keywords : Polyhydroquinoline, LiClO_4 , PEG, Hantzsch reaction, one-pot synthesis.

Introduction

1,4-Dihydropyridyl compounds are interesting and very important compounds because of their pharmacological properties as Ca^{2+} channel blockers¹. They have emerged as one of the most important classes of drugs for the treatment of cardiovascular diseases, such as nifedipine, nicardipine, amlodipine and other related derivatives, which are effective in treatment of hypertension². 1,4-Dihydropyridines possess a variety of biological activities, such as vasodilator, bronchodilator, antiatherosclerotic, antitumor and antidiabetic³. Quinolines having a 1,4-dihydropyridine nucleus are also very important compounds because of these pharmacological properties. Thus, the synthesis of this heterocyclic nucleus is of very importance.

Therefore, several methods have been developed for the synthesis of polyhydroquinoline derivatives by using various catalysts including pTSA⁵, I_2 ⁶, ionic liquid⁷, morpholine⁸, $\text{H}_3\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}/\text{TiO}_2$ ⁹, $\text{Yb}(\text{OTf})_3$ ¹⁰, L-proline¹¹, HY-zeolites¹², Bakers' yeast¹³, CAN ¹⁴, palladium(0), nanoparticles¹⁵, scolecite¹⁶ etc. However, the use of high temperatures, expensive metal precursors, catalysts that are harmful to environment, and longer reaction times limit the use of these methods. Therefore, the search for a better method for the synthesis of polyhydroquinoline derivatives is still the need of the day.

Recently, polyethylene glycol (PEG) is found to be an interesting solvent system due to their inexpensive and eco-friendly nature, high thermal stability, ease of workup, and the ability to act as phase transfer catalysts¹⁷. Furthermore, LiClO_4 has emerged as a powerful promoter in many chemical processes and in different organic media¹⁸⁻²². To the best of our knowledge, however, LiClO_4 promoted synthesis of polyhydroquinoline derivatives has not been reported till date.

In the present work, we report here a novel protocol for the synthesis of polyhydroquinolines via one-pot reaction of aldehydes, dimedone, ethyl acetoacetate, and ammonium acetate catalyzed by LiClO_4 in PEG.

Results and discussion

As a model reaction, we selected dimedone (1 mmol), benzaldehyde (1 mmol), ethyl acetoacetate (1 mmol), ammonium acetate (2 mmol) and LiClO_4 (0.1 mmol) in ethanol under refluxing conditions for a certain period of time required to complete the reaction. The reaction mixture was then allowed to cool to room temperature and stand for half an hour. The resultant precipitate was isolated by filtration and washed with cold ethanol affording the crude product in 88% yield.

Then different solvents were investigated and the result was listed in Table 1. In general, solvent like CHCl_3 , THF and H_2O led to low yield under the corresponding

Scheme 1. Synthesis of polyhydroquinolines. Reagents and conditions : LiClO₄, PEG-400, 70 °C 1.5–2.5 h.

Table 1. Optimization of the reaction conditions on model reaction^a

Entry	Solvent	Cat. (mol%)	Temp. (°C)	Time (h)	Yield ^b (%)
1	H ₂ O	10	70	6	53
2	CHCl ₂	10	Reflux	6	65
3	THF	10	Reflux	3	79
4	Ethanol	10	Reflux	2	88
5	PEG-400	10 (5, 15)	70	1.5	94 (71, 94)
6	PEG-400	10	25	12	91

^aGeneral procedure : a mixture of benzaldehyde (1 mmol), dimedone (1 mmol), ethyl acetoacetate (1 mmol), ammonium acetate (2 mmol) and catalyst were stirred in one-pot in the solvent (2 mL). ^bIsolated yield.

conditions, but the best conversion was observed when the reaction was carried out in PEG-400. The use of just 10 mol% of LiClO₄ in stirring PEG is sufficient to push

the reaction forward. Higher amounts of LiClO₄ did not lead to significant improvement in the yield of polyhydroquinolines (Entry 5). In PEG at room temperature the reaction was complete within about 12 h. The reaction rate was increased and the reaction was complete within 1.5 h at a temperature of 70 °C, but the yield was not increased (Entry 5 and 6).

The scope and generality of the above process is illustrated with the results listed in Table 2. As shown in the Table 2, aromatic aldehydes carrying either electron donating or withdrawing substituent reacted smoothly with β-ketoesters and dimedone (5,5-dimethylcyclohexanone or 1,3-cyclohexandione) to give excellent yields of products with high purity. But more reaction time was needed and lower yield was obtained when *o*-chlorobenzaldehyde was used as the reaction substrate, which may be due to the steric effect. Furthermore, the reaction also proceeded

Table 2. Scope of one-pot synthesis of polyhydroquinolines catalyzed by LiClO₄^a

Product	R ₁	R ₂	Time (h)	M.p. (lit.) (°C)	Yield ^b (%)
5a	H	CH ₃	1.5	202–204 (203–204) ²³	93
5b	4-CH ₃	CH ₃	1.5	261–262 (260–262) ²³	95
5c	4-CH ₃ O	CH ₃	1.5	263–265 (264–266) ²³	91
5d	4-Cl	CH ₃	1.5	249–250 (250–251) ²³	96
5e	2-Cl	CH ₃	2.5	208–210 (209–210) ²³	85
5f	3-CH ₃ O, 4-CH ₃ O	CH ₃	1.5	201–203 (201–203) ²⁴	97
5g	H	H	1.5	239–240 (240–241) ¹⁴	94
5h	4-CH ₃	H	1.5	241–242 (242–243) ¹⁴	93
5i	4-CH ₃ O	H	1.5	193–195 (193–195) ¹⁴	90
5j	4-Cl	H	1.5	234–235 (234–235) ¹⁴	96
5k	2-Cl	H	2.5	207–209 (nr ^c)	86
5l	3-CH ₃ O, 4-CH ₃ O	H	1.5	192–193 (192–194) ²⁵	95
5m ^d	4-Cl	CH ₃	1.5	249–250 (250–251) ²⁴	92

^aGeneral procedure : a mixture of aromatic aldehyde (2 mmol), dimedone (2 mmol), ethyl acetoacetate (2 mmol), ammonium acetate (3 mmol) and LiClO₄ (10% mol) were stirred at refluxing in one-pot in PEG-400 (5 mL). ^bIsolated yield. ^cNo data reported for this compound.

^dNH₄HCO₃ was used as the material instead of NH₄OAc.

successfully when using ammonium bicarbonate as the source of "NH₃" instead of ammonium acetate (product 5 m). All products can be separated by filtration conveniently after the reaction completed, washed with cold ethanol, and then characterized by NMR directly without any other purification. The filtrate including PEG and LiClO₄ was dried at 70 °C prior to use for next run in model reaction. And it was found that the recovered catalyst shows good yield with three successive reactions (Table 3).

Table 3. Recovery and reusability of catalyst

Entry	Cycle	Yield (%) ^a
1	Fresh	94
2	First	92
3	Second	91
4	Third	90

^aIsolated yield.

Experimental

All chemicals used were obtained from commercial suppliers and used without further purifications. ¹H NMR spectra were determined on a Bruker AVANCE DMX III 400M spectrometer and ¹³C NMR spectra were obtained on the same instrument, respectively. Samples were dissolved in deuterated chloroform (CDCl₃), which provided the deuterium lock for the spectrometers. Tetramethylsilane or residual chloroform was used as an internal standard. Melting points were measured using a BUCHI M-560 melting point apparatus. Reactions were monitored by thin layer chromatography (TLC) carried out on 0.25 mm silica gel plates visualized with UV light.

General procedure for the synthesis of polyhydroquinoline :

To a solution of aldehyde **1** (2 mmol), dimedone **2** (2 mmol), ethyl acetoacetate **3** (2 mmol), ammonium acetate (3 mmol) in PEG-400 (5 ml), LiClO₄ (10 mol%) was added. The reaction mixture was stirred at 70 °C for 1.5–2.5 h. The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC. After completion of the reaction, the mixture was filtered to obtain polyhydroquinolines without any other purification.

Spectroscopic data of some representative compounds :

Ethyl-1, 4, 7, 8-tetrahydro-2, 7, 7-trimethyl-4-(4-

methylphenyl)-5(6H)-oxoquinolin-3-carboxylate (5b) : Yellow solid, δ_H (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : 0.94 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.06 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.21 (3H, t, *J* 6.8 Hz, CH₃), 2.12–2.28 (4H, m, 2×CH₃), 2.24 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.33 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.06 (2H, q, *J* 6.8 Hz, CH₂), 5.01 (1H, s, CH), 6.57 (1H, s, NH), 6.99 (2H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz, ArH), 7.18 (2H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz, ArH); δ_C (100 MHz, CDCl₃) : 14.2, 19.3, 21.0, 27.2, 29.5, 32.7, 36.1, 41.0, 50.8, 59.7, 106.2, 112.2, 127.9, 128.6, 135.3, 143.3, 144.2, 148.2, 167.5, 195.5.

Ethyl-1, 4, 7, 8-tetrahydro-2, 7, 7-trimethyl-4-(4-chlorophenyl)-5(6H)-oxoquinolin-3-carboxylate (5d) : Yellow solid, δ_H (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : 0.92 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.06 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.19 (3H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, CH₃), 2.12–2.33 (4H, m, 2×CH₃), 2.36 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.06 (2H, q, *J* 7.2 Hz, CH₂), 5.02 (1H, s, CH), 6.50 (1H, s, NH), 7.16 (2H, d, *J* 7.6 Hz, ArH), 7.24 (2H, d, *J* 7.6 Hz, ArH); δ_C (100 MHz, CDCl₃) : 14.2, 19.2, 27.0, 29.5, 32.6, 36.3, 40.6, 50.8, 59.9, 105.5, 111.3, 128.0, 129.4, 131.6, 144.2, 145.8, 149.6, 167.4, 195.9.

Ethyl-1, 4, 7, 8-tetrahydro-2-methyl-4-(4-methylphenyl)-5(6H)-oxoquinolin-3-carboxylate (5h) : Yellow solid, δ_H (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : 1.96 (3H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, CH₃), 1.92–1.98 (2H, m, CH₃), 2.26 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.30–2.45 (4H, m, 2×CH₃), 2.36 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.06 (2H, q, *J* 7.2 Hz, CH₂), 5.06 (1H, s, CH), 6.28 (1H, s, NH), 6.96 (2H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz, ArH), 7.18 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, ArH); δ_C (100 MHz, CDCl₃) : 14.3, 19.1, 21.1, 27.2, 36.0, 37.1, 59.8, 106.0, 113.1, 127.8, 128.6, 135.4, 143.7, 144.4, 150.9, 167.6, 196.1.

Ethyl-1, 4, 7, 8-tetrahydro-2-methyl-4-(2-chlorophenyl)-5(6H)-oxoquinolin-3-carboxylate (5k) : Yellow solid, δ_H (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : 1.17 (3H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, CH₃), 1.90–2.00 (2H, m, CH₃), 2.31–2.48 (4H, m, 2×CH₃), 4.00–4.08 (2H, m, CH₂), 5.39 (1H, s, CH), 6.46 (1H, s, NH), 7.01–7.36 (4H, m, ArH); δ_C (100 MHz, CDCl₃) : 14.2, 19.2, 21.0, 27.4, 35.9, 36.9, 59.8, 105.3, 112.3, 127.2, 127.7, 129.6, 132.1, 133.3, 143.5, 143.1, 167.5, 195.6.

Conclusion :

In summary, we have developed a straightforward and effective method for the preparation of polyhydroquinolines via one-pot reaction of aldehydes, dimedone, ethyl acetoacetate, and ammonium acetate promoted by LiClO₄

in PEG-400. This method tolerates most of the substrates, and the catalyst/solvent system can be recycled and re-used at least three times without significant loss of activity, which conforms to “green chemistry”.

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